

Influence of Politics in Education on Effective Posting of Teachers in Government Secondary Schools in Kebbi State, Nigeria

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Abstract

The study x-rays titled Influence of Politics in Education on effective Posting of Teachers in Government Secondary Schools in Kebbi State, with a single objective to guide the study, how does influence of politics in education affect effective posting of teachers in secondary schools in Kebbi State? A descriptive survey design was adopted for the study. The population is of the study is 5177 which consist of all government secondary school stakeholders in Kebbi State during the 2022/2023 academic session, and sample of 360 was choose which falls within the range of 5000, recommended by Research Advisor 2006 and a purposive sampling technique was used to select 30% out of the six educational zones in Kebbi State. Simple random sampling was used to select 9 schools. Data was collected using the instrument title IPEETPGSS questionnaire and analyzed using statistical tools of frequency counts, percentages, mean scores, and tables. Subsequently, inferential statistics such as one-way analysis of variance was used to test the hypotheses for the study; findings from the survey study revealed that there is influence of politics in education on effective teachers' posting in government secondary schools in Kebbi State. The paper concluded that posting and transfer of teachers should be exclusively left in the hands of the supervisory agencies of government, who are saddled with such responsibility.

Keywords: Influence, Politics, Posting, Teachers, Secondary School

Introduction

Education is usually faced with avoidable challenges from the political point of view, especially in administration. It is so because the political appointees typically determine what type of management should be used for the system Muhammad (2013). They also support the components of the educational system and how it operates. For instance, the essential concepts of socialism as a political theory were about the capitalist system's widespread exploitation of the working class. Socialism is a political concept that acknowledges property as the cornerstone of the state's economic structure, which concentrates power in the hands of the people that possess property Osuji (2011). In a society where the owners of the means of production do not have to work, and the means of production are nationalized, workers have no property Muhammad (2013). Only educational reforms will be able to modify such a societal structure Muhammad (2013). The citizenry would be trained by the state, for the state, and at state institutions under a governmental mechanism with complete control over curriculum and instruction Haliru (2018). In these situations, the state authorities frequently set the curriculum's specifics, including residents' functional training Dada (2008). May include scientific training for social application may be included in the curriculum.

Mexico, Bulgaria, and Cuba are excellent examples of nations that have enacted a socialist education system Osuji (2011). The state's monopoly over education, secularism, physical and military training, political indoctrination inside and outside the classroom, and a greater emphasis on science topics are all shared characteristics of their educational system. Individual freedom and the concept of tolerance are not tolerated in these states. In contrast to these nations, France has a centralized educational approach based on its political philosophy. In France, the metropole, or central government, is in charge of all matters about education Osuji (2011). In the cases of the USA and Japan, the political ideologies of capitalism and democracy, respectively, are frequently incorporated into their highly decentralized educational systems Muhammad (2013). The national character and the national educational system are very closely related. For instance, the USA has a democratic national identity, and as a result, most components of its educational system are democratic Muhammad (2013). The political

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philosophy of nationalism has an impact on a nation's educational system as well. A group's psychological belief that they share a common viewpoint and customs based on a shared heritage is known as nationalism. These shared ancestries span racial, linguistic, religious, and geographic boundaries and frequently amplify national identity. A country's political ideology, which often includes racial issues, may significantly impact the educational system's components Dada (2008). Race can be a tribe, a nation, or a collection of states. Today's modern population is made up of people from many racial backgrounds. The decentralization and creation of a commonwealth of nations, each of which should be free to forge its own culture and national identity, served as the foundation for British colonial policy. As a result, there is a direct connection between national character and the educational system, with the former being widely acknowledged as a critical tenet of the latter Muhammad (2013). Thus, a nation's educational policy and political system are strongly intertwined.

These facts are well known to Nigerian politicians, who put education at the forefront of their campaigns for elective offices. The political parties that gained power betrayed the country for not fulfilling their campaign promises to raise educational standards Dada (2008). They usually allow extended strikes, mediocre teaching, and a lack of staff to ruin the educational system Muhammad (2013). As a result, secondary schools frequently lack the necessary resources and suffer from poor planning, bad financial and managerial practices, and a lack of dedication from the instructors, principals, and even board members. There aren't enough classrooms, and neither are there enough labs or libraries. It's a sign of decay in secondary schools, according to Osuji (2011). Education appeared set to become every state's top priority in the final decades of the 20th Century. Education, which was initially considered a luxury of wealthy nations and individuals, a way of preparing people for their station in life, or at the very least, a way of caring for the children until they were old enough to work, came to be seen as both a fundamental right of the individual and a requirement for the state.

As mentioned, our political system must necessarily extend into public education, making schools nothing more than tools for carrying out political dictates. For instance, throughout the past thirty years, the federalization of education has occurred through both direct and indirect mechanisms. Bureaucracy is inevitable in government policy and practice, of course. But the main problem with the demand for hierarchy and organization is that politics prioritizes leadership qualities over technical knowledge. No politician can possess the knowledge and experience required in all the diverse areas that a leader must handle, especially in positions like governor and president, as stated by Osaghee and Irabor (2018). The direct function of the president and governors concerning education has expanded significantly throughout the accountability era in education some years back, frequently with education as they prioritized education during their campaigns. According to Toljaduola, Odumade, and Agbajeola (2009), one significant flaw in that development has been a trickle-down effect from presidents and governors to state superintendents of education and school board chairs and members; individuals with little to no experience or expertise as educators or scholars attain leadership positions in charge of developing and implementing education policy. To put it another way, appointees and presumed reformers who, while frequently well-intentioned, lack considerable competence or experience in education are the faces and voices currently leading the drive for education reform in Nigeria. Given the above, its clear that there are many abnormalities in education in Nigeria and Kebbi State in particular, especially in education administration and proper policy implementation Haliru (2018). That is why we undertook the research to identify whether or not the level at which politics has influence on education, mainly on how teachers are posted to their various places of primary assignment.

One of the most essential components of the educational system is the teacher. They are a necessary component of every educational program. Their presence guarantees that the curriculum will be completed. The good academic accomplishment of student depends on the quality of the teachers. The researcher discusses hiring, posting, and retention in this regard. The recruitment process is the starting point for staff appointment at this stage. The school system must have classified its intentions as to the quality and quantity of the staff it wants, it must have an idea of the salary range it proposes to offer, and it must also understand other conditions of service that it will provide.

There are two types of recruitment according to Ojo (2018) Internal Recruitment and External Recruitment. Promotions or transfers among current employees can fill job openings in an organization. It is possible to pick people (for upgrades) formally by posting job openings and inviting employees to submit bids or informally by looking through a skills inventory to find people who meet the requirements (Ojo, 2018). The company can use departmental memos, periodicals, and bulletin boards to inform current employees about job openings. All interested workers will have an equal opportunity to apply in response to the internal advertisement. Employees will have to react to the advertisement with external candidates with whom they must compete if it is both "internal" and "external."

Skills inventory and personnel appraisal: Here, it is taught that a list of names with pertinent abilities and qualities makes up an employee's skills inventory. Names, education, current employment, position and location; previous jobs; training;

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performance; salary levels; and other details will be included. According to Ojo (2018), the talent inventory thus offers a simple method of looking for workers with unique skills or abilities who can fill open roles or positions that have just been created.

There are several external sources of recruitment, according to Ojo (2018). Unsolicited Applications "Casual" applications or "Walk-ins" can be a significant source of recruiting for unskilled and, to a lesser extent, for highly skilled employees. Many employees receive applications via letters or in person from several persons. Public Recruiting Agencies- In many nations, employment agencies serve as the primary or only recruitment method into the civil service. Each federation-level state in Nigeria has its civil service commission and the federal one. Additionally, each state has a local government service commission that hires particular kinds of local government employees. Private Recruiting Agencies or consultancy (recruiting) companies offer placement services for job seekers and referrals for specific positions that are advertised with them. In Nigeria, hiring through private agencies has gained popularity due to the significant growth in the number of such firms over time.

Recruitment advertisements may be published in newspapers, magazines, trade or professional journals, bulletins posted in supermarkets, and on radio or television. Some companies use their staff to fill open positions. Employees are informed of relevant information regarding job openings and the abilities required, and they subsequently share this information with friends and family members who may possess these skills and be looking for work. In Nigeria, employee recruitment is prevalent. Almost all staff levels are covered, including junior or unskilled, senior, and executive human resources. For instance, according to Ojo (1998, p. 190), approximately 33% of respondents obtained their initial jobs through family members, 27% through friends, and 19% through merit.

Educational Institutions or Organizations quiet often keeps in touch with various educational institutions, including universities, polytechnics, technical and vocational institutes, and others. They are reliable sites for finding young candidates with different formal educations. Specific candidates are recommended to employers by counselors or placement officials at some of these institutions. Labour Unions in some developed nations like the United Kingdom, the United States of America, and Canada, this source of hiring is more pertinent. Construction, seafaring, and ductwork are some areas and professions where it is primarily functional. Employers typically send requests for new hires to the "Union Hiring Hall" for proper action. The union members who have been jobless the longest or the most senior are typically given preference when job opportunities are documented. Professional Associations or groups in Nigeria offer assistance in finding qualified candidates for new, senior, and experienced positions.

Recruitment Authority in the Secondary Schools Management Board, the Arabic Board, the State Universal Basic Education Board, and the Ministry of Science and Technical Education are all tasked with carrying out the State Ministry of Education's recruitment duties for teachers. The Ministry of Education hires educators for grades 0 through 7 and higher. The Kebbi State Government must pay their salary and benefits. Because the Civil Service Rules and Regulations serve as the authority's guide, the three categories of appointments that are available are temporary, contract, and permanent/pensionable. In Contract Appointment, special educators whose services are occasionally still required are hired on a contract basis, typically after retirement. As for Permanent and Pensionable Appointment, a two-year probationary term is required for permanent and pensionable appointments. To be confirmed and promoted, an officer must pass all mandatory exams required for his appointment. The probationary appointment may also be terminated if the officer fails the required examination. Any officer must possess the National Certificate of Education (NCE) minimum qualification to be eligible for permanent employment and retirement benefits in the teaching sector. For Temporary Appointment, teachers are placed under two years of observation before their appointments are confirmed, meaning the officer must have been effective and efficient in their duty before the work is guaranteed. However, the appointment may be terminated if the officer is found guilty.

In general overview, the teacher is entirely different in terms of skills, personality, and dedication to the profession to which they belong. The beginners among them have basic knowledge, which according to the National Policy on Education (2014), the Nigeria Certificate of Education (NCE), while the professionals have advanced degrees. They have different perceptions of their presentation, and while some have the view of starting their presentation from simple to complex, others have a different perspective. Thus, if you assign them to handle students, you find that each has their way of presentation and a different way of classroom management. When management moves a teacher to a new position, it may do so at the teacher's request or through administrative action. When a transfer request is made, a gap or a series of issues arise for the school administration, the teacher, and the students.

The educational process is sensitive when it comes to personnel issues. It must be determined which aspects of hiring and posting teachers should continue to be handled by the federal government and which could be managed more effectively at the state level. The government should almost probably continue to exercise some control over the total number of teachers engaged

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in the public sector (and, consequently, over expenditure levels). It is also proper for the government to establish eligibility requirements. However, choices about the pattern of staffing in the schools and the selection of specific instructors may be made locally, even at the school level.

In terms of consistently supplying their schools with qualified teachers and keeping those in service, Nigeria's educational system is dealing with a severe problem. Some estimates show that more than a third of the country's instructors leave the teaching profession after three years, according to the National Commission on Teaching and America's Future (2009). According to more recent data, 46% of instructors quit their jobs by the conclusion of their fifth year. Specific significant issues have been identified as reasons for teachers leaving their jobs. Retirement, family problems, pregnancy/childrearing, salary/benefits, job unhappiness, and interest in moving into a better position, either inside or outside of education, could all be among them. Many of these same educators were worried about things like Low salaries, issues with student behavior, a lack of assistance, and few opportunities for decision-making participation.

Oke (2016) noted that teachers could leave their jobs as teachers and the schools where they work in a paper titled "Retention of Teachers and their Condition of Service" that was presented at the National Conference of Principals of Teacher Training Colleges held at the Ahmadu Bello University, Zaria in 1971. He observed that the rate of resignations from the teaching profession is excessive compared to other disciplines like law, medicine, and pharmacy. He claimed that teaching and attrition are widespread and not unique to Nigeria alone. However, their seriousness can vary from one nation to the other. Poor pay and a low social standing for teachers in Nigeria relative to other countries are some issues highlighted by Oke (2016). According to the Banjo Commission in erstwhile Western Nigeria, the teaching profession has been referred to as a diseased profession. The entrance requirements have historically been relatively low. The pay scales cannot be compared to other employment categories, such as the civil service. There are extremely few opportunities for promotion here, and his professional effectiveness barely impacts the teacher's career. Many people who are successful in "uplifting" themselves into grade one decide that it would be better to leave teaching and work in government instead, where they will be paid more. Dada (2008) conducted two studies on the supply and demand of school teachers in Lagos and a defunct Mid-Western state. In the Lagos study, survey questionnaires were distributed. The majority of responses were as follows:

1. Payment delays relative to the private sector
2. Lack of promotion opportunities
3. Poor service conditions
4. Our society does not value or appreciate teachers.
5. The government's lack of encouragement.

Out of the 178 questionnaires returned, 147 stressed poor conditions of service and the fact that society still looks down on teachers and the teaching profession. Several Nigerian authors have discussed these issues: The loss of skilled teachers to other industries when the teaching industry is struggling to find talented and motivated young people was previously brought up by Asiyai (2013). "The general lack of manpower has made it difficult to interest talented people in teaching, coupled with subpar service conditions, which has worsened the recruitment situation," he observed. For some reason, teaching has to compete with other professions for the attention of capable young people. Most individuals drawn are those who can't get hired for different jobs and end up teaching. This group includes the majority of secondary school teaching professionals.

Objective of the study

To assess influence of politics in Education on effective posting of teachers in government secondary schools in Kebbi State, Nigeria.

Research Question

Does influence of politics in education affect effective teachers posting in Government Secondary Schools in Kebbi State?

Hypothesis

There is no significant difference between Influence of politics in Education and effective posting of teachers in government secondary schools in Kebbi state, Nigeria

Methodology

A descriptive survey research design was adopted for the study, which, according to Ishaya in Haliru (2018), is appropriate for a study involving a large population of respondents. The population of the study is 5177 which consist of all

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government secondary school stakeholders in Kebbi State during the 2022/2023 academic session, and sample of 360 was chosen comprising 18 principals, 327 teachers, 10 SBMC members, and 10 quality assurance officials and a purposive sampling technique was used to select 30% out of the six educational zones in Kebbi State. Simple random sampling was used to select 9 schools. Data was collected using the instrument titled IPEETPGSS questionnaire with five points Likert scale options which include; strongly agree (5), agree (4), undecided (3), disagree (2), and strongly disagree (1) for positive statements. Also, the scoring was reversed for negative statements. The questionnaire consists of section one, personal data of the respondents; section two, 10 option statements for hypotheses testing. A reliability test of the instrument was conducted with Cronbach alpha 0.84 to determine the reliability of the instrument and the paper was analyzed using statistical tools of frequency counts, percentages, mean scores, and tables. Subsequently, inferential statistics such as one-way analysis of variance was used to test the hypotheses for the study.

Results

The analysis of the bio-data, which contain the status and gender of the respondents, was done and presented in Table 1.

Table 1: Analysis of Personal Data of the Respondents

s/n	Bio-Data	Category	Frequency	Percentage	Cumulative Percentage
1.	Status	Principal	18	4.9	4.9
		Teacher	327	89.7	94.6
		SBMC officials	10	2.7	97.3
		Quality Assurance	10	2.7	100
2.	Gender	Male	294	80.5	80.5
		Female	71	19.5	100
3.	Qualification	NCE	185	50.1	50.1
		N D	20	5.5	55.6
		B. ED	105	28.8	84.4
		M.ED	45	12.9	97.3
		Others	10	2.7	100

Source: Field survey, 2022

Table 1, shows that 18 principals, 327 teachers, 10 SBMC officials, and 10 Quality Assurance representing 4.9%, 89.7%, 2.7%, and 2.7%, respectively, constitute the study's respondents. A total of 294 respondents representing 80.5%, were males, while 71, representing 19.5%, were females. On qualification, 185, representing 50.1%, had NCE, 20 representing 5.5%, had M.ED, 105 representing 28.8%, and had B.ED, 45 representing 12.9%, had M.ED, and 10 representing 2.7% had other qualifications. What are the educational implications of the results?

Research Question

How does Influence of Politics in Education affect effective Teachers Posting in Government Secondary Schools in Kebbi State?

Table 2: Mean Score of Respondents on the Influence of Politics in Education for Effective Teacher's Posting In Government Secondary Schools In Kebbi State

S/N	Item statement	Respondent	N	MEAN
1	English teachers are posted to schools based on Influence of politics in education in government secondary schools in Kebbi state.	Principals	18	3.0
		Teachers	327	3.1

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2	Mathematics teachers are posted to schools based on the Influence of politics in education in government secondary schools in the state.	SBMC	10	3.8
		Q/Assurance	10	3.6
		Principals	18	2.9
		Teachers	327	2.9
3	Qualification is considered when posting staff due to Influence of politics in education in secondary schools in the state.	SBMC	10	2.5
		Q/Assurance	10	4.2
		Principals	18	2.7
		Teachers	327	2.8
4	The posting of staff based on seniority is based on the Influence of politics in education in secondary schools in the state.	SBMC	10	3.7
		Q/Assurance	10	4.1
		Principals	18	3.8
		Teachers	327	2.8
5	Influence of politics in education affects staff posting to rural areas in secondary schools in Kebbi State.	SBMC	10	1.6
		Q/Assurance	10	2.5
		Principals	18	1.4
		Teachers	327	3.4
6	Gender is considered in a staff posting due to the Influence of politics in education in secondary schools in the state.	SBMC	10	2.7
		Q/Assurance	10	3.3
		Principals	18	2.4
		Teachers	327	2.6
7	Influence of politics in education influences staff posting to urban areas in secondary schools in Kebbi State.	SBMC	10	3.6
		Q/Assurance	10	3.6
		Principals	18	3.7
		Teachers	327	3.1
8	Influence of politics in education encourages favoritism in staff posting in secondary schools in the state.	SBMC	10	3.4
		Q/Assurance	10	3.6
		Principals	18	2.5
		Teachers	327	3.1
9	The appointment of principals is influenced by politics in education in secondary schools in the state.	SBMC	10	4.6
		Q/Assurance	10	2.8
		Principals	18	2.1
		Teachers	327	2.9
10	Appointing inexperienced staff to the principal cadre is influenced by the politics in education in secondary schools in the state.	SBMC	10	1.0
		Q/Assurance	10	2.5
		Principals	18	2.9
		Teachers	327	2.9
		SBMC	10	1.9
		Q/Assurance	10	2.3

Source: Field survey, 2022

From Table 2, item 1 revealed principals having a mean score of 3.0, teachers 3.1, SBMC officials 3.8, and Quality Assurance (Q A) 3.6. It shows that all the respondents accepted the item statements. Item 2 showed that principals have a mean score of 2.9, teachers 2.9, SBMC 2.5, and QA 4.2, which implies acceptance of one and three were rejected. Item 3 was accepted by two respondents and dismissed by the other two, with the mean score for principals 2.7, teacher 2.8, SBMC 3.7, and QA 4.1, respectively. Item 4 was accepted by the principals but rejected by three other respondents with a mean score of 3.8, 2.8, 1.6, and 2.5, respectively. Item 5 had a mean score of 4.4 for principals, teachers 3.4, SBMC 2.7, and QA 3.3, indicating acceptance by three and rejection by one. Item 6 showed that principals had a mean score of 2.4, teachers 2.6, SBMC 3.6, and QA 3.6. It shows the two accepted and rejected. Item 7 was obtained by principals, teachers, SBMC, and QA, with the respective mean scores of 3.7, 3.1, 3.4, and 3.6. Item 8 has the mean score of 2.5, 3.1, 4.6 and 2.8 for principals, teachers, SBMC and QA, indicating two accepted and rejected. Item 9 has the mean score of 2.1, 2.9, 1.0 and 2.5 for principals, teachers, SBMC, and QA, respectively, indicating all were rejected. Item 10 has the corresponding mean score of 2.9, 2.9, 1.9, and 2.3 for principals,

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teachers, SBMC, and QA; all respondents left it. It was revealed, therefore, that Influence of politics in education has negative impact on teachers posting in government secondary schools in Kebbi State.

Hypothesis

There is no significant difference in the Opinion of Principals, Teachers, Quality Assurance Officials, and SBMC Representatives on The Influence of Politics in Education on effective Teachers' Posting in Government Secondary Schools in Kebbi State.

Table 3: Summary of Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) on The Influence of Politics on effective Teachers Posting in Government Secondary Schools in Kebbi State.

Posting	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	1.839	3	0.613	0.338	0.798
Within Groups	655.291	361	1.815		
Total	657.130	364			

Source: Computed from hypothesis testing, 2022

The result of the null hypothesis states that there is no significant difference in respondents' opinion on the Influence of politics in education on teachers posting in Government Secondary Schools in Kebbi State is retained. It is because the calculated significant value (p) of 0.84 is higher than the 0.05 alpha level of significance set for the study. It implies that the responses of the respondents were in agreement.

Discussion of Findings

The findings of this study revealed the Influence of Politics in education on effective teachers' posting in Government Secondary Schools in Kebbi State; this is because posting in rural and urban areas is influenced by politics, and the appointment of Head teachers / Principals is influenced by politics also posting of staff is gender-sensitive, male staff are posted more in the rural areas than their female counterpart. It is in agreement with the statements of Ogunu, in Osuji (2011) posited that politics influence the appointment, promotion, and transfer of teachers. The author further observed that in the school situation, staff personnel administration forms an essential responsibility of the school administration in achieving the school's goals in particular and in education in general. Similarly, Mgbodile (2004) stated that politics influences the posting and promotion of teachers in schools. They also mentioned that there is an influence of politics in the sponsorship of seminars, workshops, and conferences.

Conclusion

The Interference of politics in education on teachers' posting in Kebbi State is a reality; this is because posting and transfer of teachers are not done based on standard criteria for staff, which include specialization, years of working experience, and seniority among others but is due to the influence of politics. It maybe because, during the cause of this study, it was observed that there are teaching staff that are posted and or transferred based on their interest or the interest of their political Godfather, without consideration of the teaching service policy.

It was also observed that some of the officials at the Ministry of Education, Secondary Schools Management Board, Arabic, and Islamic Board, on most occasions, do the posting or transfer of teachers based on the instructions of the politicians.

Recommendations

Posting and transfer should be exclusively left in the hands of the supervisory agencies of government, who are saddled with such responsibility.

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